

Metal Complexes of some Model Peptide Derivatives. Part-VII. Equilibrium Study of the Interaction of Iron(III) with *N*-Salicyloylglycine and Phosphoric Acid in Binary and Ternary Systems

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Combined potentiometric pH-titration and spectrophotometric study on the interaction of Fe^{III} with *N*-salicyloylglycine, *o*-HO-C₆H₄CONHCH₂COOH and phosphoric acid in binary and ternary systems provided the evidence of formation of varieties of complexes. The ligand provided bidentate (O, O) chelation to Fe^{III} at low pH (<3) through the phenolate oxygen atom and the carbonyl oxygen atom of the amide group and terdentate (O, N, O) chelation at higher pH through the phenolate oxygen, deprotonated amide nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen atoms. Fe^{III} showed a profound tendency to form mixed ligand hydroxo complexes even at low pH.

THE red brown protein, ferritin is widely distributed in plants and animals¹. It sequesters iron(III) in a soluble and non-toxic form and functions as a readily available storage of iron(III)². It is an unique bioinorganic molecule in which iron(III) is associated with the protein in the bulk phase as a polymer of ferric hydroxide and ferric orthophosphate (ca. 8 : 1) in a macromolecular form containing upto 4500 iron(III) atoms per molecule. Elucidation of the nature and mode of iron(III)/protein/hydroxide/phosphate interaction is complicated for obvious reason. Although model studies³⁻⁷ with small ligands of well known structural and bonding modes have provided a lot of information, many of these are yet to be explored. The present paper describes an equilibrium study of the interaction of iron(III) in binary and ternary systems with phosphate and *N*-salicyloylglycine (H₂L), which, in addition to its amide and carboxylic functions has a phenolic moiety that has specific binding affinity for Fe^{III}. The results of the present study will be useful in understanding the nature of ternary iron(III)-hydroxo-phenolate and quaternary iron(III)-hydroxo-phosphate-phenolate interactions prevailing in the natural systems.

Experimental

The ligand *N*-salicyloylglycine (H₂L) was prepared and purified by the known procedure⁸. Ferric nitrate solution was prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated alkali-free ferric hydroxide in dilute nitric acid providing sufficient excess to suppress the hydrolysis of Fe^{III}(aq.) ions. Concentrations of free acid and iron(III) were determined

by combined ion-exchange and complexometric determination¹⁰. All other reagents were of A.R. quality. pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 digital pH meter (accuracy ±0.01 pH) using a special glass electrode in conjunction with a SCE. The following solutions, each of initial volume 25 ml were pH-metrically titrated with a standard 0.1 M NaOH solution in aqueous 50% (v/v) ethanol medium maintaining a constant ionic strength $\mu=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO₃) as the background electrolyte: (1), 0.01 M HNO₃; (2), (1)+0.0005 M Fe^{III} nitrate; (3), (1)+0.005 M H₃PO₄; (4), (2)+0.005 M H₃PO₄; (5), (1)+0.005 M H₂L; (6), (2)+0.005 M H₂L; (7), (1)+0.0005 M H₂L; (8), (2)+0.0005 M H₂L; (9), (8)+0.0005 M H₃PO₄; (10), (2)+0.0005 M H₃PO₄+0.0015 M H₂L; (11), (2)+0.0015 M H₃PO₄+0.0005 M H₂L.

pH-titration data are presented in Fig. 1. Equilibrium constants were evaluated by subjecting the pH-titration data after incorporating correction for the use of mixed solvent¹¹⁻¹³ to SCOGS computer programme¹⁴ executed by a B 6700 computer at the Regional Computer Centre, Calcutta. Hydrolysis constants of Fe^{III}(aq.) ions were evaluated from the pH-titration data of solution (2). Proton ligand constants, formation constants of binary and ternary complexes were evaluated by analysis the pH-titration data.

Results and Discussions

Binary Fe^{III} - H₃PO₄ equilibria [Fe^{III} : H₃PO₄ = 1 : 10] : pH-titration curve (Fig. 1, curve 4) of H₃PO₄ in the presence of Fe^{III}, ([H₃PO₄] ≥ 10 [Fe^{III}]),

showed the release of three protons per Fe^{III} in the pH range slightly lower than the buffer

Fig. 1. pH-titrations curves of Fe^{III} in absence and in presence of H_2PO_4 and H_2L at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ in aqueous 50% (v/v) ethanol medium, ionic strength $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3). (1), 0.01 M HNO_3 ; (2) (1) + $0.0005 \text{ M Fe}^{\text{III}}$; (3), (1) + $0.005 \text{ M H}_2\text{PO}_4$; (4), (2) + $0.005 \text{ M H}_2\text{PO}_4$; (5), (1) + $0.005 \text{ M H}_2\text{L}$; (6), (2) + $0.005 \text{ M H}_2\text{L}$; (7), (1) + $0.0005 \text{ M H}_2\text{L}$; (8), (2) + $0.0005 \text{ M H}_2\text{L}$; (9), (8) + $0.0005 \text{ M H}_2\text{PO}_4$; (10), (2) + $0.0005 \text{ M H}_2\text{PO}_4$; (11), (2) + $0.0015 \text{ M H}_2\text{PO}_4$ + $0.0005 \text{ M H}_2\text{L}$.

region (curves 5 and 7) corresponding to the deprotonation equilibria, $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-$, suggesting the formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2^+$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_3$ in successive steps. As the hydrolytic equilibria of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{aq.})$ ion was overlapping with the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ equilibria, the hydroxo complexes, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_m(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_n$ (where, $m \geq 1$, $n \leq 3$ and $(m+n) \leq 3$) were also taken care of while evaluating the equilibrium constants. More than 60% of Fe^{III} was present as $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_3$ (Fig. 2) at the commencement of precipitation ($\text{pH} \approx 3.4$), where $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^+$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)$ contributed less than 25%. $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)$ was formed in increasing amounts on raising the pH. The simple binary species, viz. $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2^+$ were negligibly small at the commencement of precipitation. The simple hydroxide, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, could not however be identified in the entire pH range (2–3.4) studied. However, the complex, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$ was present to the extent of 15–20% even at $\text{pH} \approx 2$.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves for the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (1 : 10) system : (1) H_2PO_4 , (2) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, (3) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$, (4) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, (5) $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$, (6) $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2^+$, (7) $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_3$, (8) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^+$, (9) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)$, (10) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)$, FM = Fe^{2+} , FL = H_2PO_4^- .

Binary $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{L}$ equilibria ($[\text{Fe}] : [\text{H}_2\text{L}] = 1 : 1$ and $1 : 10$): The complexation equilibria of the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{L}$ system occurred as pH values lower than that corresponding to deprotonation of carboxylic moiety of the ligand (Fig. 1, curves 5, 6, 7 and 8). 1 : 1 $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{L}$ mixture showed a sharp inflection at $\text{pH} > 4$ with release of $3\text{H}^+/\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$. 1 : 10 $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{L}$ mixture showed an inflection with turbidity at $\text{pH} \approx 7$ with release of $6\text{H}^+/\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$. Mole-ratio study of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{L}$ mixtures at $\text{pH} < 7$ by spectrophotometric method¹⁵ (λ_{max} , 450 nm) indicated 1 : 2 $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{L}$ as the highest complex formed in this metal-ligand system. $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_2\text{L}$ mixtures assumed a violet colour (λ_{max} , 525 nm) at $\text{pH} \approx 2$ indicating the coordination of phenolic oxygen to Fe^{III} . The λ_{max} value sharply shifted to 450 nm at $\text{pH} \approx 4.5$; at still higher pH it showed very little shift to lower wavelengths indicating a remarkable increase of the ligand field strength around Fe^{III} in going from pH 3 to 4.5. This could be explained by assuming (O, O) bidentate chelation of Fe^{III} by the phenolate oxygen and the carbonyl oxygen atom of the amide bond at low pH (<3) to form the complexes, $\text{Fe}(\text{HL})^{2+}$ (1) and $\text{Fe}(\text{HL})_2^+$ (2) having the carboxylate group uncoordinated due to stereochemical reason and these complexes undergo amide deprotonation¹⁶⁻¹⁸ according to equilibrium (1),

in between pH 3 and 4.5 with a concomitant structural change that replaces the amide carbonyl oxygen by deprotonated amide nitrogen in the complexes 1 and 2 to produce the complexes, $\text{Fe}(\text{L}-\text{H})$ (3) and $\text{Fe}(\text{L}-\text{H})_2^{3-}$ (4), respectively.

Such a structural change could enable the carboxylate oxygen atom to bind Fe^{III}. Thus the ligand

(L-H)³⁻ provides terdentate ($\bar{O}, \bar{N}, \bar{O}$) chelation to Fe^{III} and hence a stronger ligand field¹⁸. A similar pH variation study of the absorption spectra of Fe^{III} under identical condition in the presence of salicyloyldimethylamine which could offer only (O, O) bidentate chelation (5) to Fe^{III} showed no change of λ_{max} value from 520 nm in going from pH 2 to 4.5, only the absorption intensity lowered slightly.

The following proton-ligand and Fe^{III}-ligand species, H₂L, HL⁻, Fe³⁺, Fe(OH)²⁺, Fe(OH)₂⁺, Fe(OH)₃, Fe(HL)²⁺, Fe(L-H), Fe(OH)(HL)⁺, Fe(OH)₂(HL), Fe(OH)(L-H)⁻, Fe(OH)₂(L-H)²⁻, Fe(OH)₃(L-H)³⁻ were assumed to occur in the 1:1 Fe^{III}-H₂L system and the additional complexes, viz. Fe(HL)₂⁺, Fe(HL)(L-H)⁻, Fe(L-H)₂²⁻ were assumed to occur in the 1:10 system. In the 1:10 system (Fig. 3) the concentration maxima of Fe(OH)²⁺, Fe(OH)₂⁺ and Fe(OH)₃ occur at pH 2.5, 3.5 and 5, respectively. Fe(L-H) appears at pH $\geq$ 2 and reaches maximum ($\approx$ 20%) at pH $\approx$ 4. Fe(L-H)₂²⁻ makes its first appearance at pH $\approx$ 4, its concentration increases sharply and reaches $\approx$ 100% at pH $\approx$ 7.5. The hydroxo complexes, Fe(OH)(L-H)⁻, Fe(OH)₂(L-H)²⁻ and Fe(OH)₃(L-H)³⁻ could not be identified. The major ($\approx$ 75%) Fe^{III} species at low pH values (2 < pH < 3) in the 1:1 system is Fe(OH)²⁺, while Fe(OH)₂⁺ is the major ($\approx$ 50%) species in between pH 3 and 4 (Fig. 4). The complex, Fe(OH)(L-H)⁻ was formed to the extent of $\geq$ 5% at the commencement of

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves for Fe^{III}-H₂L (1:10) system: (1) H₂L, (2) HL⁻, (3) Fe(OH)²⁺, (4) Fe(OH)₂⁺, (5) Fe(OH)₃, (6) Fe(L-H), (7) Fe(L-H)₂²⁻, (8) Fe(OH)(L-H)⁻, (9) Fe(OH)₂(L-H)²⁻, (10) Fe(OH)₃(L-H)³⁻, FM = Fe³⁺, FL = L²⁻.

Fig. 4. Species distribution curves for Fe^{III}-H₂L (1:1) system: (1) H₂L, (2) HL⁻, (3) Fe(OH)²⁺, (4) Fe(OH)₂⁺, (5) Fe(OH)₃, (6) Fe(HL)₂⁺, (7) Fe(HL)₂⁺, (8) Fe(OH)(HL)⁺, (9) Fe(OH)₂(HL), (10) Fe(OH)(L-H)⁻; FM = Fe³⁺; FL = L²⁻.

precipitation at pH > 4, when the concentration of Fe(OH)₃ was $\geq$ 65%. Contribution of the complexes Fe(HL)₂⁺, Fe(L-H), Fe(OH)(LH)⁺, Fe(OH)₂(HL) are negligible.

Ternary Fe^{III}-H₃PO₄-H₂L equilibria: The ternary 1:1:1 Fe^{III}-H₃PO₄-H₂L equilibria was assumed to involve the following complex species: H₃PO₄, H₂PO₄⁻, H₂L, HL⁻, Fe³⁺, Fe(OH)²⁺, Fe(OH)₂⁺, Fe(OH)₃, Fe(H₂PO₄)²⁺, Fe(OH)(H₂PO₄)⁺, Fe(HL)₂⁺, Fe(L-H), Fe(OH)(HL)⁺, Fe(OH)(L-H)⁻, Fe(H₃PO₄)(HL)⁺, Fe(H₂PO₄)(L-H)⁻, Fe(OH)(H₂PO₄)(L-H)²⁻ and Fe(OH)₂(H₂PO₄)(L-H)³⁻. Estimates of formation constants of ternary Fe^{III}-H₃PO₄-H₂L complexes could be obtained from statistical consideration with the aid of equilibrium (2),

$\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4) + \text{Fe}(\text{X}) \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{X}) + \text{Fe}$ (2)
 where, $\text{X} = \text{HL}^-$ and $\text{L} - \text{H}^{2-}$ ions, for which the equilibrium constants $10\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}}$ is related¹⁹ to the formation constants of $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)$, $\text{Fe}(\text{X})$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{X})$ complexes according to equation (3),

$$\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}} = \log \beta_{\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{X})}^{\text{Fe}} - \log K_{\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)}^{\text{Fe}} - \log K_{\text{Fe}(\text{X})}^{\text{Fe}} \quad (3)$$

the charges being dropped for simplicity. The formation constants of the quaternary $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_n(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{(n+1)-}$ complexes (where, $n=1, 2$) could be obtained with the aid of equilibrium (4),

for which the equilibrium constant $10\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}}$ could be obtained by equation (5).

$$\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}} = \log \beta_{\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_n(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})}^{\text{Fe}} - \log K_{\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_n(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})}^{\text{Fe}} - \log K_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{NH}} \quad (5)$$

The constant $K_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{NH}}$ corresponds to the hydrolytic equilibrium (6),

of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{aq.})$ ion and the other constants are of self-descriptive in nature.

$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$ are the major Fe^{III} containing species at pH 2.5 in the ternary 1 : 1 : 1 $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} - \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{L}$ system (Fig. 5). $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ reaches maximum ($\approx 25\%$) at $\text{pH} \approx 3.0$. Nearly 80% of Fe^{III} is present as $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$ at $\text{pH} \geq 3.5$.

Fig. 5. Species distribution curves for $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} - \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{L}$ (1 : 1 : 1) system : (1) H_2PO_4 , (2) H_2L (3) HL^- , (4) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, (5) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, (6) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, (7) $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$, (8) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$, (9) $\text{Fe}(\text{HL})^{2+}$, (10) $\text{Fe}(\text{L} - \text{H})$, (11) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{HL})^+$, (12) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$, (13) $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{HL})^+$, (14) $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$, (15) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$, (16) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$, FM = Fe^{2+} , FL = H_2PO_4^- .

The binary $\text{Fe}(\text{L} - \text{H})$ and ternary $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$ complexes are formed only in very small amounts and $\text{Fe}(\text{HL})^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{HL})^+$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{HL})^+$, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$ could not even be identified. Distribution profiles of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$, H_2PO_4 and H_2L are indicative of the equilibria (7) and (8) as possible

routes of formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$ at $\text{pH} \geq 2.5$. Almost identical values of the formation constants of the complexes are obtained using two other ratios, 1 : 1 : 10 and 1 : 10 : 1 for $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} - \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{L}$ of which the concentration pH profiles for the different complex species are almost superimposable with those of the 1 : 1 : 1 system.

Negative $\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}}$ values for $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{HL})^+$, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{HL})^+$, $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$ are indicative of lower stability of these complexes. The major Fe^{III} containing species in all these three ternary systems is the complex, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$ ion. Favoured formation of this quaternary hydroxo complex, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$, as evident from the positive $\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}}$ value (Table 1) even in the presence of large excess of H_2PO_4 and H_2L ligands, reflects the profound

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS^a ($\log \beta_{\text{Fe}(\text{A})(\text{B})(\text{C})}^{\text{Fe}}$)^b OF Fe^{III} COMPLEXES WITH H_2PO_4 AND H_2L AND $\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}}$ VALUES AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$ IN AQUEOUS 50% (v/v) ETHANOL MEDIUM, IONIC STRENGTH $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3)

Complex ^a $\text{Fe}(\text{A})(\text{B})(\text{C})$	$\log \beta_{\text{Fe}(\text{A})(\text{B})(\text{C})}^{\text{Fe}}$	$\Delta\log K_{\text{Fe}}$
$\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$	4.21	—
$\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{2+}$	7.52	—
$\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$	11.85	—
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^+$	2.33	+ 0.05
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)$	- 0.44	+ 0.15
$\text{Fe}(\text{HL})^{2+}$	8.05	—
$\text{Fe}(\text{L} - \text{H})$	6.98	—
$\text{Fe}(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$	8.76	—
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{HL})^+$	5.19	- 0.93
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{HL})$	3.17	- 0.08
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$	4.20	- 0.85
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$	1.40	- 0.78
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$	- 2.08	- 0.46
$\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{HL})^+$	12.38	- 0.03
$\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^-$	6.88	- 4.31
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$	10.37	+ 1.11
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{L} - \text{H})^{2-}$	1.40	- 0.68

^aLimit of error in the constants $\pm 0.02 - 0.04$ in log scale.

^bUsing: $\text{p}K_{\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4}^{\text{H}}$, 3.26, $\text{p}K_{\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4}^{\text{H}}$, 7.48, $\text{p}K_{\text{H}_2\text{L}}^{\text{H}}$, 3.98, $\text{p}K_{\text{HL}}^{\text{H}}$, 8.83, $\text{p}K_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{H}}$, 1.93, $\text{p}K_{\text{Fe}}^{2\text{H}}$, 4.80 and $\text{p}K_{\text{Fe}}^{3\text{H}}$, 8.60. ^aA, B and C represent ligands, viz. H_2PO_4^- , OH^- , HL^- , $\text{H} - \text{L}^{2-}$ etc.

affinity of Fe^{III} for the hydroxo ligand (OH). Such an observation is of tremendous biological significance in the context of nature's selection of Fe^{III} as the co-factor in many enzymic processes.

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